

Participatory tools

BRAINSTORM AND DISNEY'S METHOD

CLARIFY THE BIG IDEA TOGETHER: IDEA GENERATION AND DEFINITION

How can people work together to define the idea?

A project will be built around an idea for change or innovation. The initial idea will typically emerge from one of three sources:

- A pre-existing collective that wishes to continue working together
- A person/group wishing to respond to a call for projects
- A person/group who has an idea and is looking for a framework to develop it.

The emergence and definition of the idea is an essential step, and the more it is developed collectively with the first partners engaged, the more robust the project is likely to be. This preparation foreshadows what will follow. It is important to take the time to listen to and understand each partner's vision. Moreover, mobilizing potentially interested people as soon as possible greatly facilitates the project.

How to solve it

Creativity is welcome at this early stage of project design (before the project officially exists), taking the time to imagine together a motivating project. It can be helpful to approach a variety of people who may or may not eventually be part of the actual project team. This helps to flesh out the idea, including knowledge of the context, expertise, etc. Some steps to do this can be:

- 1/ Sharing with each actor the analysis of the existing situation and current issues: a shared and solid vision is needed to build a new project.
- 2/ Identifying together what could be done and the necessary skills required to achieve it.
- 3/ Defining the first foundations of the project: what, why, with whom, etc.

Word of advice:

You quickly set up rules of confidentiality within the project planning group. This stage requires preparation time. The idea needs to evolve and mature. A valuable investment is to meet regularly, which helps

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build a trustful work environment and facilitate co-innovation during the project.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Brainstorm – The Swiss Army knife: takes us out of all our worries, simply and effectively.

Description of the tool

- **What:** exchange ideas, explore a subject, share representations
- **How long:** depends on the size of the group, 30' to 1h
- **How many:** 3 to 20
- **What you'll need:** sticky notes, markers, whiteboard, or flip chart

Steps:

- The facilitator states the question and makes sure that it is clear to everyone. In explaining the instructions, the facilitator specifies that one idea should be written on each sticky note (to facilitate sorting later) in felt-tip pen (for good legibility from a distance).
- Participants think on their own and write their ideas on sticky notes. Depending on the time and the objective, the facilitator can limit the number of sticky notes per participant.
- Participants share their sticky notes:
 - They take turns to stick the sticky notes on a flip chart or a board. They can group the sticky notes according to common ideas. The facilitator makes sure that they understand the fundamental ideas expressed in the sticky

notes rather than interpreting them from their own perspective.

- The facilitator collects a sticky note that the participant explains. The facilitator then asks if any participants have a similar idea and picks it up. They then pick up another idea.
- The facilitator groups the sticky notes by central ideas or recapitulates the groupings already made by writing the themes and materialising the groupings. They ask the participants if these groupings suit them and ask whether they can think about other options or other ideas.
- The facilitator takes a photo of the final picture to report back.

Testimony of the use

Sylvain Quiédeville, FiBL, Switzerland – case study deputy of the project Agrolora

Agrolora is a local Swiss multi-actor project. It tests the functionality, reliability, and scalability of an automatic irrigation system.

Some participants used the 'brainstorm' tool at the very beginning of the creation process, during the inception phase of the project and also during the project delivery. The aims were to work on the project's idea, develop the idea, and exchange about the possible funding. The team were already used to working in this way within their organization. The team that carried out the brainstorming was composed of four actors from the same organization but with different skills. They used the brainstorming

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method to develop and move forward on specific ideas. They often did this spontaneously, as it has become a working habit.

Tips:

Logistics:

- If the analysis is delayed, have the participants write down their names
- Provide for a pair of facilitators

For the facilitator:

- Have a precise question
- Texts to be combined with expression because sometimes sticky notes are limiting on ideas on complex subjects
- The talent of the facilitator to agglomerate the sticky notes: this comes with practice

For the participants:

- Keep always in mind the "one idea per sticky notes" rule
- Provide one large felt-tip pen per participant: it's big, so they are pushed to write a word, not a novel
- Write in capitals for clearer reading

Another tool:

[Disney's method](#)

Description of the tool

- **What:** Stimulate creativity, produce ideas (and make decisions)
- **How long:** 30 to 40 min
- **How many:** from 5 to 15
- **What you'll need:** flip chart, sticky notes, markers

Steps:

- Space is divided into three parts: creative space, realistic space, and ethical space. In practice, the flip chart can be moved to different places in the room.
- The protocol starts in the creative space. The facilitator writes down the question to be dealt with at the top of the page. It is a brainstorming phase, where the important thing is to set no limits and let your imagination run wild. Participants can put their ideas on sticky notes to express more freely. The facilitator records all the answers.
- Once the time is up, the facilitator moves the flip chart to another part of the room: the realistic space. It consists of going through the proposals one by one, clarifying them if necessary, and then deleting those that are not financially or materially realistic. It is important here to focus only on material barriers.
- Finally, the flip chart is moved again, this time into the ethical space. It is here that, with the remaining proposals, the group will eliminate those that would go against the project's ethics. The facilitator lists the proposals and asks the group whether there is an objection.

